

A filtering method for FES-based hybrid systems

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Abstract—The adoption of hybrid functional electrical stimulation (FES) and exoskeletons represents a potential solution for upper-limb assistance. The aim of this paper is to propose and validate a novel FES artifact filtering method and to verify its performance when integrated in a closed-loop FES driven by the ipsilateral electromyographic (EMG) upper limb signals. The obtained results demonstrated the effectiveness of the approach in retrieving the volitional EMG signal enabling a participant to perform daily tasks with an 80% success rate.

Index Terms—Adaptive filter, Functional Electrical Stimulation (FES), Stimulation artifact

I. INTRODUCTION

Hybrid robot-Functional Electrical Stimulation (FES) systems represent a potential solution for upper-limb motion assistance of patients with neurological disorders. The integration of these two systems enhances motor re-learning and supports accurate task execution in terms of speed, trajectory and movement fluidity [1]. Closed-loop FES, where the stimulation parameters are modulated according to the patient’s ipsilateral residual volitional electromyographic signal (vEMG), is fundamental to make hybrid systems able to provide assistance customized on the real motor performance. Nonetheless, in ipsilateral closed-loop FES (i.e., both the stimulation and monitoring of residual muscle activity occur on the same limb), the vEMG signal is superimposed by M-wave and two FES-related artifacts, i.e. *i*) a transient stimulation (e.g. a spike with amplitude greater than usual EMG signal); *ii*) a post stimulus exponential voltage-decay due to slow charge dissipation [2]. Although the software solutions proposed in the literature have achieved good results, these approaches have only been tested on simulated signals or in unrealistic scenarios. The aim of this paper is to advance the state of the art on FES for upper-limb motion assistance by proposing and preliminary validating a closed-loop FES driven by the ipsilateral EMG signals. To this end, a novel method for FES artifact filtering was proposed and off-line compared with a pre-existing approach. Subsequently, the proposed method was integrated in a closed-loop FES to on-line assist a healthy participant to perform two Activities of Daily Living (ADLs).

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Fig. 1. Representative participant during the execution of the pouring task

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The proposed method sequentially applies the Notch Filter Series and the Adaptive Filter (NFS+AF) to extract volitive contraction from the acquired signal. The NFS removes the stimulation frequency and its harmonics from the EMG signal bandwidth, but its efficacy was evaluated only in off-line applications. The AF divides the EMG signal into frames, estimates the artifact from the current frame using a linear combination of the previous six ones and considers as vEMG the difference between the current frame and the estimated artifacts. The NFS+AF was compared with AF that demonstrated the best performance among the literature filtering methods [2].

The filtering methods were tested on 10 healthy participants (5M/5F, 26.0±1.8 years). The experimental setup (Fig. 1) included: six EMG Trigno Wireless sensors for the following hand extrinsic muscles: 1) Flexor Carpi Radialis (FCR); 2) Extensor Carpi Ulnaris (ECU); 3) Flexor Digitorum Superficialis (FDS) 4) Extensor Digitorum Communis (EDC); 5) Abductor Pollicis Brevis (APB); 6) Extensor Pollicis Longus (EPL). These muscles were selected as the superficial muscles most involved during the execution of upper-limb ADLs; the multichannel electric stimulator STG4008 to deliver a symmetric biphasic square wave [3]; six couples of circular commercial auto-adhesive and superficial electrodes; a 500 g water bottle sensorized with Force Sensing Resistors (FSRs) for grasping force measurement.

The participants performed two ADLs (i.e., drinking, pouring) under three different modalities (five repetitions each): *i*) via FES (i.e., no voluntary muscle contraction) aimed to determine the maximum force F_{MAX} the participant was able to apply on the object thanks to the stimulation; *ii*) in a volitive

Fig. 2. Workflow of the NFS+AF filtering method for the extraction of the vEMG. **A** vEMG+FES (blue) and vEMG raw (red) signals; **B** vEMG+FES signal after the application of NFS and AF; **C** Comparison between raw vEMG and vEMG extracted. Each signal is represented in time and frequency domain.

way, where FES was not adopted and the participant was asked to use only the voluntary signal, $e(t)$, to grasp the object with a force equal to $F_{MAX}/2$; *iii*) a mixed approach, where both FES and volitive signals were adopted to generate a muscular signal $s(t)$ necessary to apply a grasping force equal to F_{MAX} . In this final mixed approach, the F_{MAX} was equally distributed between the stimulation and the voluntary contraction. The use of the same force value in the second and third modality allowed for a comparison between the signal $e(t)$ and the signal $\hat{e}(t)$ obtained applying the filtering method to $s(t)$.

To evaluate the performance of the FES artifacts filtering methods and compare them, the following widely adopted performance indicators were extracted [2]: *i*) variation of the Signal-to-Noise Ratio (ΔSNR) computed before and after the filtering. Positive values of ΔSNR indicate a noise power reduction compared with $e(t)$; *ii*) variation of the Normalized Root Mean Square Error ($\Delta NRMSE$): negative values indicate a reduction of difference between $e(t)$ and $\hat{e}(t)$; *iii*) Power Reduction (PR): values of PR close to 1 indicate that $\hat{e}(t)$ is comparable with $e(t)$ in terms of power.

Once the analysis was completed, a closed-loop FES strategy driven by EMG signals was developed and preliminary tested on a healthy participant. This system enabled on-line monitoring of upper-limb muscle activity, the extraction of vEMG through the development of the proposed method and then the proportional modulation of stimulation as in [4]. The participant performed the two ADLs (five repetitions each) with the contribution of FES applied to the non-dominant upper-limb mimicking a paretic one. The delivered stimulation current was modulated using as reference the myoelectric activity of dominant upper-limb in order to achieve task execution with the same performance of the dominant one.

A value of 0 or 1 was assigned to each repetitions depending if it was completed or not. Therefore, a Success Rate (SR) was introduced as the percentage of successfully completed tasks compared to the total.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A qualitative analysis of the effects of NFS+AF on a representative participant muscle are reported in Fig.2. The

Fig. 3. Performance of the two filtering methods in terms of ΔSNR (A), $\Delta NRMSE$ (B) and PR (C). The + sign indicates the outlier. * indicates a statistically significant difference (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $P < 0.05$)

results reported in Fig. 3 show that NFS+AF significantly (Wilcoxon signed-rank test, $P < 0.05$) outperformed the AF in terms of ΔSNR (from 65% to 83%), $\Delta NRMSE$ (from -82% to -91%) and PR (from 8 to 3). Therefore, NFS+AF represents a progress beyond the state-of-art since it was able to remove FES artifact making the two signals (i.e., $e(t)$ and $\hat{e}(t)$) comparable both in the time and frequency domain. The proposed closed loop FES system was evaluated in terms of Success Rate achieving a value of 80%. It demonstrated the system enables the participant in performing the two ADLs. Such value could be increased by reducing the approach computational burden (the current value is 500 ms), increase the task execution time and the number of participants.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, a closed-loop FES strategy was developed and on-line preliminary validated to assist a healthy participant to perform two upper-limb ADLs. The obtained results demonstrated the efficacy of NFS+AF in retrieving vEMG outperforming the AF literature method. The obtained SR value showed the efficacy of the proposed approach in on-line assisting an healthy participant during upper-limb ADLs. Future works will be devoted to reduce the computational burden, test the system first on additional healthy participants and then on patients with neurological disorders and integrate it with an exoskeleton.

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